

SURVEILLANCE CARD_ Hepatitis E_Pathogen detection in effluents from farms and abattoirs in high-risk sites in high-risk seasons

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Pathogen detection in effluents from farms and abattoirs in high-risk sites in high-risk seasons.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of an increase in incidence. Early detection of the introduction of the pathogen into a farm, or a new watershed (or river system). Target for risk-based surveillance: risk period and/or risk areas.
3	Target species and group	Environmental samples.
4	Target sector / production type	To be defined/reported.
5	Geographical area covered	Risk areas, e.g., water used in shellfish production or for soft fruit and vegetable irrigation in areas with dense pig production.
6	Age group	To be defined/reported.
7	Sampling point and strategy	Effluent water samples taken on production sites.
8	Sampling time period	Risk period: after heavy rains or after spreading liquid pig manure on the fields or any other occasion linked to an increased risk of contamination of water. Alternatively, year-round sampling, if previous evidence does not indicate a time period of increased risk.
9	Sampling matrix	Effluent water samples (surface water, irrigation water, water samples in shellfish production sites, etc).
10	Type of disease indicators	Antigen detection (viral RNA).
11	Sampling unit	Water samples as outlined in the different protocols, e.g., the WHO guidelines for poliovirus environmental surveillance (1) or EN / ISO standards.

12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Not applicable.
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Different PCR protocols exist for the detection of HEV-1 to HEV-4 (broadly reactive PCR primers or genotype specific). Identification and typing of the agent can be achieved by PCR, followed by sequencing and molecular characterization. In addition, real-time RT-qPCR can be utilized for pathogen quantification in positive samples (2). Whole genome sequences and epidemiological information can be shared with a supranational database and genome repository maintained by HEVnet RIVM .
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	The component contributes to case detection and possibly to compare relative risks across geographical areas, but as this is a biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population (convenience sampling) it cannot be used directly to estimate the system sensitivity.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	<i>Francisella tularensis</i> , <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> , <i>Giardia</i> spp., <i>Cryptosporidia</i> spp., <i>Burkholderia pseudomallei</i> , <i>Yersinia pestis</i> , Western equine encephalitis virus, Eastern equine encephalitis virus, Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus, Ebola virus, and other water-borne pathogens (3), SARS-CoV-2 (4). <i>Uncommonly performed: Leptospira</i> spp. (5).
18	References	1) WHO (World Health Organization), 2003. Guidelines for Environmental Surveillance of Poliovirus Circulation. Available online: https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/67854 . 2) Iaconelli M, Bonanno Ferraro G, Mancini P, Suffredini E, Veneri C, Ciccaglione AR, Bruni R, Della Libera S, Bignami F, Brambilla M, De Medici D, Brandtner D, Schembri P, D'Amato S and La Rosa G, 2020. Nine-Year Nationwide Environmental

	<p>Surveillance of Hepatitis E Virus in Urban Wastewaters in Italy (2011-2019). <i>International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health</i>, 17(6), 2059. doi: 10.3390/ijerph17062059.</p> <p>3) Ramírez-Castillo FY, Loera-Muro A, Jacques M, Garneau P, Avelar-González FJ, Harel J and Guerrero-Barrera AL, 2015. Waterborne pathogens: detection methods and challenges. <i>Pathogens</i>, 4(2):307–334. doi: 10.3390/pathogens4020307.</p> <p>4) Kitamura K, Sadamasu K, Muramatsu M and Yoshida H, 2021. Efficient detection of SARS-CoV-2 RNA in the solid fraction of wastewater. <i>The Science of the Total Environment</i>, 763, 144587. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144587.</p> <p>5) Wynwood SJ, Graham GC, Weier SL, Collet TA, McKay DB and Craig SB, 2014. Leptospirosis from water sources. <i>Pathogens and Global Health</i>, 108(7) 334–338, DOI: 10.1179/2047773214Y.0000000156.</p>
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